

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

CONNECTION CALCULATION WITH INTERFERENCE FOR IMPACT LOAD

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Abstract

The value of the impact load and the values of the maximum and minimum contact pressure in the connection with interference are determined.

Keywords: Gear wheels, impact force, maximum and minimum contact pressure.

Problem substitution: In mechanical engineering, interference connections are widely used for large, and especially dynamic loads [1,2,3].

Often in gears, wheels are placed on a shaft with an interference fit (Fig. 1). In the manufacture of gears, the distances between the teeth almost always differ from each other, which causes additional dynamic impacts in the engagement of vibration and contributes to an increase in the noise level during operation [4]. Therefore, when transmitting torque with a gear train with straight teeth, shocks occur between the teeth. These shocks have a negative effect on the strength of the wheel with an interference shaft.

Solution of the problem: This article considers the problem of determining the contact pressure between the shaft and the gear wheel connected to it with straight teeth under the action of an impact force.

Let us determine the value of the acting force on the teeth of the gear upon impact. For the purpose of this, we write the expressions for the kinetic moment for the driven wheel relative to the axis of the shaft during the impact. For the purpose of this, we write the change in the moment of momentum of the driven wheel relative to the central axis of rotation during the impact:

$$J_{z_2} \omega_2 - J_{z_2} \omega_{02} = S \cdot h, \quad (1)$$

where S - is the shock impulse acting on the driven wheel; J_{z_2} - moment of inertia of the driven wheel; ω_{02} and ω_2 are the angular velocities of the driven wheel at the beginning and at the end of the impact, respectively; $h = R_0 \sin \gamma$ - the length of the

perpendicular lowered from the center of rotation of the driven wheel to the line of action of the impact force.

After the impact, the kinetic energy of the driven wheel changes. Then the expression of the theorem on the kinetic energy of the system for the driven wheel after the impact will be:

$$\frac{J_{z_2} \omega_2^2}{2} - \frac{J_{z_2} \omega_{02}^2}{2} = A, \quad (2)$$

where A - is the work done by the impact force,

$$A = \frac{S \cdot h}{\tau};$$

τ - impact time.

Multiplying each side (1) ω_1 and ω_2 separately, we get:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} J_{z_2} \omega_{02} \omega_2 - J_{z_2} \omega_{02}^2 &= S \cdot h \cdot \omega_{02} \\ J_{z_2} \omega_2^2 - J_{z_2} \omega_{02} \omega_2 &= S \cdot h \cdot \omega_2 \end{aligned} \right\}$$

From here we determine that

$$S = \frac{J_{z_2}}{h} (\omega_2 - \omega_{02}). \quad (3)$$

If we accept that the impact is made in τ time, then the value of the impact force will be:

$$F = \frac{J_{z_2}}{h \cdot \tau} (\omega_2 - \omega_{02}). \quad (4)$$

The value ω_1 is determined by the formula (10) of work [4]:

$$\omega_1 = \frac{\frac{R_0 r_0}{\left[R_0 \cos \alpha + (R_0 + r_0) \operatorname{tg} \alpha \cdot \sin \left(\alpha - \frac{\pi}{z_1} \right) \right]^2 + r_0^2 \sin^2 \frac{\pi}{z_1}} \cdot \frac{J_{z_1}}{J_{z_2}}}{\frac{r_0^2 \cos \alpha \cdot \operatorname{tg} \left(\alpha - \frac{\pi}{z_1} \right)}{R R_0 \sin(\alpha - \psi)} - \frac{J_{z_1}}{J_{z_2}}} \cdot \omega_{01}$$

where R_0 and r_0 are the initial radius of the driven and driving wheels; - R outer radius of the driven wheel; Z_1 - the number of teeth of the drive wheel; ω_{01} and ω_1 are the angular velocities of the driving wheel before and after the impact.

Let's define the value ω_2 depending on ω_1 . According to Fig. 1, we determine that

$$\omega_2 \cdot R_0 = \omega_1 \cdot r_0.$$

From here we determine that

$$\omega_2 = \frac{r_0}{R_0} \cdot \omega_1, \tag{6}$$

$$\omega_{02} = \frac{r_0}{R_0} \cdot \omega_{01}.$$

Then, taking into account (6) in (4), we get:

$$F = \frac{J_{Z_2} r_0}{h R_0 \tau} (\omega_1 - \omega_{01}). \tag{7}$$

As can be seen from formula (7), with decreasing impact time, the impact force increases. This has a negative effect on the strength of the teeth of the wheels. In order to determine the value of the maximum and minimum contact pressure on the contact surfaces, we select a coordinate system with the origin O_2 (Fig. 1), draw the axis y through the point of the contact line, at which the contact pressure is the maximum value. In accordance with [5], we assume that the contact pressure from the minimum value to the maximum varies according to a sinusoidal law depending on the angle γ . This angle is numerically equal to the angle between the two radii connecting the center of the wheel, respectively, with the considered connection point and the point at which the contact pressure has a maximum value. Thus

$$q = q_{\min} + k \sin \frac{\gamma}{2}, \tag{8}$$

where q - is the contact pressure at the considered point; $q_{\min}$ - minimum contact pressure; $k \sin \frac{\gamma}{2}$ - variable component of the contact pressure.

Let us write the conditions for the equilibrium of the acting forces, taking into account the impact force F .

$$\left. \begin{aligned} f \int_0^{2\pi} \cos \gamma \cdot dN + F \cos(\alpha + \psi) &= 0 \\ - \int_0^{2\pi} \cos \gamma \cdot dN - F \sin(\alpha + \psi) &= 0 \\ a \cdot f \cdot N - F \cdot h &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\}, \quad (9)$$

where f - is the coefficient of friction; $dN = qald\gamma$ - elementary normal force; β - the angle between the axis y and the direction of the impact force; a - radius of the contact surface; α - engagement angle.

From the joint solution of the first two equations (9), we find:

$$f = \operatorname{ctg}(\alpha + \psi). \quad (10)$$

From formula (10) it can be seen that the friction coefficient of the contacting surfaces is equal to the tangent of the engagement angle.

The formula $dN = qald\gamma$, taking into account expression (8), will be:

$$dN = (q_{\min} + k \sin \frac{\gamma}{2})ald\gamma, \quad (11)$$

where l - is the length of the connection.

After appropriate substitutions and calculations from the second equation (9), we determine:

$$k = \frac{3F}{4al} \cdot \operatorname{co}(\alpha + \psi) \quad (12)$$

or

$$k = \frac{3J_{Z_2} r_0 (\omega_1 - \omega_{01})}{4alhR_0 \tau} \cdot \sin(\alpha + \psi). \quad (13)$$

From the third equation (9), we have:

$$N = \frac{Fh}{fa}. \quad (14)$$

Integrating (11) from zero to 2π and equating in (14), we get:

$$q_{\min} = \frac{F}{2\pi al} \left[\frac{h}{fr} - 3 \cos(\alpha + \psi) \right]; \quad (15)$$

$$q_{\max} = q_{\min} + k = \frac{F}{2al} \left(\frac{h}{\pi fa} + 0.445 \cos(\alpha + \psi) \right). \quad (16)$$

As an example, we calculate the value of the impact force and the values of the maximum and minimum contact pressure with these data: $P = 20$ N; $a = 20$ mm; $l = 50$ mm; $r_0 = 30$ mm; $R_0 = 60$ mm;

$$J_{Z_2} = \frac{mR_0^2}{2}; \quad h = R_0 \cos \alpha; \quad \alpha = 20^\circ;$$

$f = 0.1$; $n_{01} = 900$ об/мин; $Z_1 = 18$; $Z_2 = 36$; $\tau = 0,07$ сек. After calculation we get $F = 1714$

kN; $q_{\max} = 805.58$ kN/cm²; $q_{\min} = 692.7$ kN / cm², which are significant values, they must be taken into account in the calculations of connections with an interference fit, when the connection is affected by an impact force.

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